

S6 b

TYPE OF INTERACTIONS	HYDROPHOBIC		HYDROGEN	
	Chain A (Pediocin) (Blue)	Chain B (LipoXc) (Red)	Chain A(Pediocin) (Blue)	Chain B (LipoXc) (Red)
Chain ID	Chain A (Pediocin) (Blue)	Chain B (LipoXc) (Red)	Chain A(Pediocin) (Blue)	Chain B (LipoXc) (Red)
Residue Number	ASN 27 ALA 30 LEU 31 ALA 32 TRP 33 ALA 34 THR 35	TYR 199 ARG 195 LEU 200 PHE 160 HIS 162 ASP 196 THR 190	GLY 37 HIS 38 ASN 41 LYS 43	LYS 142 ALA 265 GLU 139 GLN 203